

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

INFLUENCE OF FORMATION MODES ON THE PROPERTIES OF FIBROUS MATERIALS BASED ON POLYPHENYLENE SULFIDE

Garbaruk V.Yu.,

postgraduate

*V.A. Belyi Metal-Polymer Research Institute
of Belarus NAS, Belarus*

Goldade V.A.

Dr. Tech. Sci., Professor

*V.A. Belyi Metal-Polymer Research Institute
of Belarus NAS, Belarus*

Abstract

The influence of a functional additive and formation conditions on the properties of filter fibrous materials based on blends of polyphenylene sulfide and polypropylene was studied. It was shown that with increasing polypropylene content in the blend, the average fiber diameter increases. The presence of a dispersed additive contributes to a slight increase in fiber diameter, while additional heat treatment leads to an even greater increase. It was found that the introduction of a dispersed additive leads to an increase in the degree of material crystallinity, and changes in the physical and mechanical properties: sample shrinkage decreases and their rigidity increases.

Keywords: polyphenylene sulfide, fiber diameter, degree of crystallinity, filtration efficiency, transmittance, shrinkage

Purification of liquids and gases is an integral part of both most industrial processes and everyday human life. The presence of large quantities of impurities in the environment, whether liquid or solid, degrades the performance of devices and subsystems, reducing their overall service life and efficiency, and also negatively impacts the health of living organisms and the environment when contaminated media come into contact with the biosphere. Inclusions up to several tens of micrometers in size are the most difficult to remove from sub-meter-velocity flows and constitute the bulk of the total contaminant mass, which has a negative impact on mechanisms and the human body [1].

The most effective and, at the same time, cost-effective method of filtering this type of contamination from media is the use of non-woven polymer fibrous-porous materials, whose large specific surface area and mechanical properties meet modern purification requirements [2]. A sufficiently wide range of fiber-forming polymers allows for flexible variation of the characteristics of the resulting products and the selection of the necessary solution based on purification requirements. Polyolefins are most frequently used as they are widely available and inexpensive materials that are easy to process and subsequently dispose of [3-5].

To purify media characterized by high temperatures or aggressiveness to "classic" filter polymers, materials with a more complex chemical structure are used, in particular polyphenylene sulfide. However, often, when non-trivial tasks arise involving the separation of liquid or solid contaminants, pure polymeric materials cannot provide the required filtration efficiency. In such cases, functional additives are introduced into the polymer bulk, designed to change the nature of the interaction at the phase boundary and, as a result, improve the filtration properties of the spatial

structure of the microfibers. In addition, the properties of fibrous materials are significantly affected by technological processing modes, in particular, additional heat treatment or exposure to strong electric fields [6]. However, there is no consensus on the influence of external factors directly affecting the production of such products [7].

The aim of this work is to investigate the influence of functional additives and formation modes on the properties of filter elements made of fibrous materials based on mixtures of polyphenylene sulfide and polypropylene.

This study utilized materials produced by meltblowing. Meltblowing (*MB*) is a simple, versatile, and widely used extrusion-based technology that generates continuous nano/microfibers, typically forming a randomly oriented web [8]. *MB* fiber products (in the form of mats or cylinders) are formed directly from molten polymer without controlled stretching. The optimization criterion for the process conditions is achieving the best performance characteristics of *MB* materials. All other things being equal, these characteristics depend on two structural parameters: the fiber diameter d and the density ρ (or porosity) of the fibrous framework.

In this work, we investigated the effect of a nano dispersed filler, as well as additional IR and heat treatment, on the purification efficiency and physic mechanical properties of fibrous-porous filter materials (FPFM) obtained by melt blowing from mixtures of polyphenylene sulfide (PPS) and polypropylene (PP). The samples were made in the form of cylindrical filter elements obtained under the same operating conditions of the extrusion equipment. Dispersed nano clay – montmorillonite (MMT) with a particle size of 3–5 nm and a content of 0.1 wt. % in the mixture was used as a modifying filler. Such a low filler content is due to the

technological difficulties of forming an air-polymer torch when spraying the melt. Heat treatment of the samples was carried out in an oven at a temperature of 150 °C for 4 hours, a ceramic infrared emitter IKN-101 manufactured by NOMACON ODO (Belarus) was used as an IR emitter.

Six groups of PPS-based samples with different PP contents (wt.%) were studied: 0; 2.5; 5.0; 7.5; 10; 15. Within each group, the samples differed in the presence or absence of a modifier and heat treatment. The average fiber diameter was determined using a MED D45T optical microscope (Levenhuk Optics Ltd., USA), the degree of crystallinity was determined by differential scanning calorimetry on a DSC 214 Polyma device (Netzsch – Gerätebau GmbH, Germany). Filtration efficiency and transmittance were determined on a SIGF-1 stand (LLC Scientific and Technical Center LARTA, Belarus). In addition, the degree of shrinkage (relative change in the length of a cylindrical sample after heat treatment) and the depth of steel indenter penetration into the sample material were determined.

The results of the study are presented on the table.

It is evident that with increasing PP content, the average fiber diameter increases (from 33 to 47 μm), with the presence of MMT contributing to a slight increase in fiber diameter, and additional heat treatment leading to an even greater increase. The increase in fiber diameter with increasing PP content in the blend is explained by its higher MFI ($< 6 \text{ g}/10 \text{ min}$) than that of PPS ($> 30 \text{ g}/10 \text{ min}$). The presence of dispersed particles in the melt somewhat reduces melted flowability, leading to an increase in fiber diameter.

The degree of crystallinity of the samples changes slightly depending on the PP content in the mixture. However, it is noteworthy that in each group, an increase in the degree of crystallinity of the samples is observed with the introduction of dispersed filler. This indicates that the filler particles, even at such low concentrations, initiate crystal formation.

Filtration efficiency is quite high for samples in all groups; however, it is not possible to establish a pattern in how this indicator varies depending on melt composition and the presence of heat treatment. Filtration efficiency can be indirectly assessed by the particle transmission coefficient, which also varies slightly depending on the melt component content and the presence or absence of heat treatment.

Significant differences are observed in physical and mechanical properties. Firstly, low shrinkage is observed for all types of samples based on PPS and PP blends. Secondly, the presence of MMT in the mixture after heat treatment of the samples further reduces shrinkage (e.g., samples 7, 8, 11, 12). Moreover, the rigidity of these samples increases significantly. For example, the indenter penetration depth for samples 4, 7, 8, 11, 12, 15, 16, and 18 is 0.96–5.5 mm, compared to samples made from PPS+PP blends (17.4–22.0 mm).

Conclusion

Thus, as a result of studying the influence of functional additive and formation modes on the properties of filter fibrous materials based on blends of polyphenylene sulfide and polypropylene, the following was established:

- with increasing polypropylene content in the blend, the average fiber diameter increases, with the presence of a dispersed additive contributing to a slight increase in fiber diameter, and additional heat treatment leading to an even greater increase;
- the degree of crystallinity of the samples changes slightly depending on the PP content in the blend; however, in each group, an increase in the degree of crystallinity of the samples is observed with the introduction of a dispersed filler;
- all types of samples based on PPS and PP blends exhibit low shrinkage; the presence of MMT in the blend after heat treatment of the samples further reduces shrinkage, while the rigidity of these samples increases significantly.

Sample characteristics

Samples			d , μm	Cryst. %	Ef., %	K , %	$\Delta l/l$, %	h , mm
Group	Number	Composition						
1	1	Pure PPS	33	36	87,79	0,1422	-	22
	2	Pure PPS + Heat treatment	34		81,92	0,2094	15,0	2,1
2	3	PPS+2.5% PP	36		86,75	0,1492	-	18,5
	4	PPS+2.5% PP + Heat treatment	37		87,80	0,1391	4,22	2,2
3	5	PPS+5% PP	34	39	90,56	0,1136	-	18,8
	6	PPS+5% PP +MMT	38	41	87,84	0,1532	-	18,1
	7	PPS+5% PP + Heat treatment	34		88,07	0,1279	2,68	4,0
	8	PPS+5% PP +MMT + Heat treatment	41		85,15	0,1690	0,96	3,9
4	9	PPS+7.5% PP	38	37	88,11	0,1335	-	18,8
	10	PPS+7.5% PP +MMT	41	40	80,31	0,2276	-	18,4
	11	PPS+7.5% PP + Heat treatment	40		86,74	0,1541	1,82	3,0
	12	PPS+7.5% PP +MMT + Heat treatment	44		79,20	0,2337	1,57	3,6
5	13	PPS+10% PP	37	37	82,85	0,1927	-	20,5
	14	PPS+10% PP +MMT	42	42	88,77	0,1377	-	18,3
	15	PPS+10% PP + Heat treatment	39		81,86	0,2049	0,86	3,6
	16	PPS+10% PP +MMT + Heat treatment	43		78,29	0,2318	1,11	5,1
6	17	PPS+15% PP	47		88,31	0,1323	-	17,4
	18	PPS+15% PP + Heat treatment	49		85,31	0,1702	0,31	5,5

Designations: d – average fiber diameter; Cryst. – degree of crystallinity, Ef – filtration efficiency with respect to particles $\geq 10 \mu\text{m}$ in size; K – transmission coefficient of contaminant particles; $\Delta l/l$ – relative change in the length of a cylindrical sample after heat treatment (shrinkage); h – indenter penetration depth at a temperature of 150 °C and a pressure of 0.2 MPa

References

- Liu Y., Shao H., Wang H., et al. Improvement of Air Filtration Performance Using Nanofibrous Membranes with a Periodic Variation in Packing Density. *Adv. Mater. Interfaces*, 2022, vol. 9, 2101848. <https://doi.org/10.1002/admi.202101848>.
- Goldade V. A., Zotov S. V., Garbaruk V. Yu., Kovalenko M. A., Shapovalov V. M. Fibrous-porous polymeric materials for air and gas filtration (review). *Polymer Materials and Technologies*, 2025, vol. 11 (1), pp. 6–25. DOI: 10.32864/polymmattech-2025-11-1-6-25.
- Yesil Y., Bhat G.S. Porosity and barrier properties of polyethylene meltblown nonwovens. *J Text Inst*, 2017, vol. 108 (6), pp. 1035–1040. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00405000.2016.1218109>.
- Cheng S, Muhaiminul AS, Yue Z, et al. Effect of temperature on the structure and filtration performance of polypropylene melt-blown nonwovens. *Autex Res J.*, 2020, vol. 21 (2). DOI:10.2478/aut-2019-0067.
- Pinchuk L., Goldade V., Makarevich A., Kestelman V. Meltblowing: equipment, technology, and polymer fibrous materials. Berlin: Springer-Verlag Berlin, Heidelberg, 2002, 212 p.
- Garbaruk, V.Yu. The influence of additional treatment on the cleaning efficiency and physical and mechanical properties of composite filter materials based on polyphenylene sulfide / Abstracts of reports on International Conf. "Polycomtrib-2025", Gomel: MPRI NAS of Belarus, 2025, p. 87.
- Y.-C.Lai, Y.-C.Lin, Y.-P.Liao, M.-C.Kuo, and C.-W.Chen. Optimizing Processing and Formulation Strategies for Enhanced Thermal and Chemical Stability of Meltblown Polyphenylene Sulfide Nonwovens. *Polymer Engineering & Science*, 2026, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pen.70378>.
- Goldade V., Garboruk V., Zotov S. Meltblowing as an effective technology of creating fibrous-porous materials for air and gas filtration. *ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science*, 2025, vol. 148 (08), pp. 55-66. So: <https://s-o-i.org/1.1/TAS-08-148-11> Doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.15863/TAS/>